

Offset-free Model Predictive Control of the Van de Vusse Reaction

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Abstract—This paper presents the design of the model predictive control (MPC) of the Van de Vusse reaction (VVR) with the state estimation and compares two offset-free reference tracking techniques. The control algorithm thus compensates for the mismatches between the nonlinear plant and the linearized model, as well as other unmeasurable disturbances. In the first approach, the prediction model of the linear MPC is extended by incorporating separate state and output disturbance vectors and their heuristic smoothing. The second approach considers the augmented state-space model and fully integrates the disturbance estimation into the state estimation. State estimation is achieved using the Kalman filter, which provides optimal design in the statistical framework. The effectiveness of the proposed methodology is validated through the simulation of a nonlinear model of the VVR occurring in the continuous-flow stirred tank reactor (CSTR). Simulation results demonstrate the improvement of classical MPC with the state observer by incorporating offset-free reference tracking.

Keywords—disturbances, Kalman filters, linearization, model-based control, offset, predictive control, reactor control, state estimation, target tracking

I. INTRODUCTION

Model Predictive Control (MPC) is widely used in the control of technological or chemical processes due to its ability to handle multiple-input multiple-output systems based on the defined criteria while ensuring system constraints. However, the standard linear MPC can encounter challenges with reference tracking due to mismatch between the model and the plant dynamics, as noted in [1], or when the process is affected by unmeasurable disturbances. Offset-free MPC addresses these discrepancies and provides robustness against nonzero-mean disturbances.

The commonly used approach for designing linear offset-free MPC incorporates a disturbance model, which generally assumes deterministic, constant disturbances [2], [3]. An alternative is the velocity form algorithm [4], which offers an equivalent solution to the disturbance model approach. This paper compares the third approach [5], where the disturbance estimation is based on the correction term and output error of the state observer (Kalman filter), with an extended model that integrates disturbance estimation directly within the Kalman filter update. By comparing these three offset-free MPC design approaches within a coherent framework,

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Pannocchia [6], [7] demonstrated that the two alternative formulations are particular cases of the general disturbance model approach. Furthermore, Tuan et al. [8] proposed the Disturbance-Kalman state method, which improves offset-free MPC by recursively refining state estimates using a multi-step Kalman filter to mitigate model-plant mismatches.

This paper studies the application of offset-free MPC to the Van de Vusse reaction (VVR), a nonlinear chemical process occurring in a Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) [9]. Two reference tracking strategies are analyzed: one incorporating separate state and output disturbance vectors, and another using an augmented state-space formulation with integrated disturbance estimation. The effectiveness of these methods is evaluated through simulations. The main contribution of this study is the introduction of a filtered disturbance observer, which reduces control oscillations while maintaining accurate reference tracking.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the discrete-time linear stochastic model and the state observer design using the asymptotic Kalman filter. Section III outlines the linear MPC design, while Section IV extends it with offset-free reference tracking using two different approaches. In Section V, the VVR is illustrated. Finally, Section VI presents and discusses the simulation results.

II. STOCHASTIC STATE ESTIMATION

A. Stochastic State-Space Model

Consider the linear, discrete-time, time-invariant system defined in the state-space form:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + w(k), \quad (1a)$$

$$y(k) = Cx(k) + v(k), \quad (1b)$$

where $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^r$, and $y(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the state, input, and output vectors of the system, respectively; $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, and $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ are the state, input, and output matrices of the system. The sample number $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is related to the real time $t \in \mathbb{R}$ through the sampling time $T_s \in \mathbb{R}$, with the relation $t = kT_s$.

Since we are considering a stochastic system, the process noise vector $w(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the measurement noise vector $v(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represent uncorrelated stationary random processes with zero-mean. These noises are characterized by their covariance matrices $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, given by:

$$Q = \text{cov}(w(k), w(k)) = E\{w(k)w(k)^T\}, \quad (2)$$

$$R = \text{cov}(v(k), v(k)) = E\{v(k)v(k)^T\}. \quad (3)$$

B. Kalman Filter

The Kalman filter is a linear estimator designed for stochastic systems, providing an optimal state estimate under the assumption that the process and measurement noise are zero-mean and Gaussian-distributed [10].

The state estimate by the asymptotic Kalman filter is given by the prediction and correction step:

$$\hat{x}(k) = A\hat{x}^*(k-1) + Bu(k-1), \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{x}^*(k) = \hat{x}(k) + K(y(k) - C\hat{x}(k)), \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the a priori (predicted) state estimate, $\hat{x}^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the a posteriori (corrected) state estimate, and $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ is the Kalman gain matrix.

The Kalman filter minimizes the variances of the deviation between the predicted and actual state values of the system. Let the state estimation error $x_e(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $x_e(k) = x(k) - \hat{x}^*(k)$. Then, the covariance matrix of the state estimate error quantifies the uncertainty associated with the state estimate and is defined as:

$$P = \text{cov}(x_e(k), x_e(k)) = E\{x_e(k)x_e(k)^T\}, \quad (6)$$

where $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. The steady-state covariance matrix can be determined as the solution of the discrete algebraic Riccati equation, given by:

$$P = APA^T - APC^T(CPC^T + R)^{-1}CPA^T + Q. \quad (7)$$

Subsequently, by minimizing the trace of the covariance matrix P as defined in (7), the Kalman gain matrix can be expressed as:

$$K = PC^T(CPC^T + R)^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

III. MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

Model Predictive Control (MPC) is an advanced control method that predicts and optimizes the future dynamic response of the system based on knowledge of the system model [11]. The prediction horizon p is the time frame over which the optimization is carried out. The number of generated inputs is referred to as the control horizon c , where $c \leq p$.

A. Prediction Model

The prediction model of the output MPC is developed from the nominal (deterministic) model of the controlled system (1), which is commonly represented in state-space form:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k), \quad y(k) = Cx(k). \quad (9)$$

Future states and outputs can be predicted through recursive substitution into the nominal system model (9), yielding the output prediction:

$$\hat{y}(k) = M\hat{x}(k) + N\hat{u}(k), \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{y}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{mp}$, $\hat{y}(k) = [y(k+1)^T \dots y(k+p)^T]^T$ is the predicted output vector and $\hat{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{rp}$, $\hat{u}(k) = [u(k)^T \dots u(k+p-1)^T]^T$ is the predicted input vector.

The free response prediction matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times n}$ and the forced response prediction matrix $N \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times rp}$ are defined as:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} CA \\ CA^2 \\ \vdots \\ CA^p \end{bmatrix}, \quad N = \begin{bmatrix} CB & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ CAB & CB & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ CA^{p-1}B & CA^{p-2}B & \dots & CB \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

B. Target Calculation

A feasible reference value in output MPC can be achieved by solving the optimization problem at each time step to calculate the target value. We consider the minimization of the function with respect to the steady-state values of the system's output $y_s \in \mathbb{R}^m$, state $x_s \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and input $u_s \in \mathbb{R}^r$:

$$\min_{y_s, x_s, u_s} (r(k) - y_s(k))^T Q_s (r(k) - y_s(k)), \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s. t. } x_s(k) = Ax_s(k) + Bu_s(k), \quad (12b)$$

$$y_s(k) = Cx_s(k), \quad (12c)$$

where $r(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the desired reference setpoint and $Q_s \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $Q_s^T = Q_s \succcurlyeq 0$ is the weighting matrix. The optimization problem (12) can also be defined with system constraints, such as system input constraints (17), which are detailed in Section III-D.

C. Objective Function

One of the commonly used forms of the objective function in the output MPC for tracking a non-zero reference value is:

$$J(\Delta u(k)) = \sum_{i=1}^p (y(k) - y_r(k))^T Q_y (y(k) - y_r(k)) + \sum_{i=0}^{c-1} \Delta u(k+i)^T R_d \Delta u(k+i), \quad (13)$$

where $\Delta u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^r$, $\Delta u(k) = u(k) - u(k-1)$ is the input change vector, $y_r(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the output reference. The criteria of the objective function (13) are defined by the output weighting matrix $Q_y \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $Q_y^T = Q_y \succ 0$ and the input change weighting matrix $R_d \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $R_d^T = R_d \succ 0$.

To apply the prediction model (10) in the optimization, it is essential to reformulate the objective function (13) into the following form:

$$J(\Delta \hat{u}(k)) = (\hat{y}(k) - \hat{y}_r(k))^T \tilde{Q}_y (\hat{y}(k) - \hat{y}_r(k)) + \Delta \hat{u}(k)^T \tilde{R}_d \Delta \hat{u}(k), \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta \hat{u}(k) = [\Delta u(k)^T \dots \Delta u(k+c-1)^T]^T$, $\Delta \hat{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{rc}$ is the predicted vector of input changes, and $\hat{y}_r(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{mp}$ is the predicted vector of the output reference. The matrices $\tilde{Q}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times mp}$, $\tilde{Q}_y^T = \tilde{Q}_y \succ 0$, $\tilde{Q}_y = \text{diag}(Q_y, \dots, Q_y)$ and $\tilde{R}_d \in \mathbb{R}^{rc \times rc}$, $\tilde{R}_d^T = \tilde{R}_d \succ 0$, $\tilde{R}_d = \text{diag}(R_d, \dots, R_d)$ represent the block diagonal extended weighting matrices.

In order to optimize the objective function with respect to the predicted input change vector, we define the predicted input in the following incremental form:

$$\hat{u}(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} I_r & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ I_r & I_r & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ I_r & I_r & \cdots & I_r \end{bmatrix}}_{\Psi} \Delta \hat{u}(k) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} I_r \\ I_r \\ \vdots \\ I_r \end{bmatrix}}_{\tilde{I}} u(k-1), \quad (15)$$

where $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{rp \times rc}$ is the summation matrix, $\tilde{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{rp \times r}$ is the extended unit matrix, and $I_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ is the identity matrix.

The predicted output, after substituting (15) into (10), is defined as:

$$\hat{y}(k) = N\Psi\Delta\hat{u}(k) + M\hat{x}(k) + N\tilde{I}u(k-1). \quad (16)$$

D. System Constraints

For the optimization problem, we can also define specific system constraints that arise due to the technological or safety limits of the controlled system. Specifically, we can consider the system input constraints as follows:

$$u_{\min} \leq u(k+i) \leq u_{\max}, \quad (17)$$

where $u_{\min} \in \mathbb{R}^r$ and $u_{\max} \in \mathbb{R}^r$ represent the lower and upper bounds of the system input. The input constraints (17) can also be defined for the predicted input as:

$$-\tilde{I}_{rp}\hat{u}(k) \leq -\tilde{I}u_{\min}, \quad \tilde{I}_{rp}\hat{u}(k) \leq \tilde{I}u_{\max}, \quad (18)$$

where $\tilde{I}_{rp} \in \mathbb{R}^{rp \times rp}$ is the identity matrix. To apply the input constraints as conditions for the objective function (14), we must define them in incremental form as follows:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -\Psi \\ \Psi \end{bmatrix}}_{A_c} \Delta \hat{u}(k) \leq \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{I}(-u_{\min} + u(k-1)) \\ \tilde{I}(u_{\max} - u(k-1)) \end{bmatrix}}_{b_c}, \quad (19)$$

where $A_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times rp}$, $b_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$, and n_c is the number of constraints.

The optimization problem of MPC with constraints can be formulated in the general form of quadratic programming as:

$$\Delta \hat{u}^*(k) = \arg \min_{\Delta \hat{u}(k)} \frac{1}{2} \Delta \hat{u}(k)^T H \Delta \hat{u}(k) + G^T \Delta \hat{u}(k), \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A_c \Delta \hat{u}(k) \leq b_c, \quad (20b)$$

where $H \in \mathbb{R}^{rc \times rc}$ is the Hessian matrix, $G \in \mathbb{R}^{rc}$ is the linear term vector, and $\Delta \hat{u}^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{rc}$ is the optimal input change vector, from which only the first element is used to control the system at the k -th sample.

IV. OFFSET-FREE MPC

Offset-free tracking of the output ensures the reduction of steady-state bias between the reference and the output. This deviation can arise from discrepancies between the model and the plant, or from the influence of persistent nonzero-mean disturbances. The block diagram of the offset-free MPC is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the offset-free MPC (black – current vectors, grey – previous vectors, red – tuning parameters).

A. State and Output Disturbance

The difference between the filtered value $\hat{x}^*(k)$ and the predicted value $\hat{x}(k)$ of the state is referred to as the state disturbance vector $d_x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $d_x(k) = \hat{x}^*(k) - \hat{x}(k)$. After the rearrangement of $d_x(k)$, it takes the following form:

$$d_x(k) = K(y(k) - C\hat{x}(k)), \quad (21)$$

where $d_x(k)$ represents the posterior correction of the state estimate in the Kalman filter iteration given by (5).

The output disturbance vector $d_y(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is defined as the difference between the current measured output and the current estimated output:

$$d_y(k) = y(k) - C\hat{x}^*(k). \quad (22)$$

The design of the offset-free MPC can be improved by implementing disturbance filtering with a parameter that weighs the importance of the current disturbance relative to the prior disturbance. This approach enables attenuation of the impact of state and output noise on disturbance estimates, thereby enhancing the system's control performance. By attenuating the effect of noise, the system minimizes oscillations in the control inputs.

The filtered vectors of state and output disturbance are defined as:

$$d_x^*(k) = \alpha d_x^*(k-1) + (1-\alpha)d_x(k), \quad (23)$$

$$d_y^*(k) = \alpha d_y^*(k-1) + (1-\alpha)d_y(k), \quad (24)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 \leq \alpha < 1$ is the disturbance filtering parameter, $d_x^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the filtered state disturbance vector, and $d_y^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the filtered output disturbance vector.

B. Prediction Model with Disturbance

By adding the filtered state disturbance $d_x^*(k)$ (23) and the filtered output disturbance $d_y^*(k)$ (24) to the nominal system model (9), the system model with disturbance is obtained as:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + d_x^*(k), \quad (25a)$$

$$y(k) = Cx(k) + d_y^*(k). \quad (25b)$$

The output prediction equation for the model (25) is given by:

$$\hat{y}(k) = M\hat{x}(k) + N\hat{u}(k) + D_x^*\hat{d}_x^*(k) + \hat{d}_y^*(k), \quad (26)$$

where $D_x^* \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times np}$ is the filtered state disturbance prediction matrix:

$$D_x^* = \begin{bmatrix} C & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ CA & C & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ CA^{p-1} & CA^{p-2} & \dots & C \end{bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

Additionally, the filtered state disturbance predicted vector $\hat{d}_x^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{np}$, $\hat{d}_x^*(k) = [\hat{d}_x^*(k)^\top \dots \hat{d}_x^*(k+p-1)^\top]^\top$ and the filtered output disturbance predicted vector $\hat{d}_y^*(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{mp}$, $\hat{d}_y^*(k) = [\hat{d}_y^*(k+1)^\top \dots \hat{d}_y^*(k+p)^\top]^\top$ are defined as:

$$\hat{d}_x^*(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha I_n \\ \alpha^2 I_n \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^p I_n \end{bmatrix}}_{D_{x_1}} d_x^*(k-1) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} (1-\alpha)I_n \\ (1-\alpha^2)I_n \\ \vdots \\ (1-\alpha^p)I_n \end{bmatrix}}_{D_{x_2}} d_x(k), \quad (28)$$

$$\hat{d}_y^*(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha^2 I_m \\ \alpha^3 I_m \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{p+1} I_m \end{bmatrix}}_{D_{y_1}} d_y^*(k-1) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} (1-\alpha^2)I_m \\ (1-\alpha^3)I_m \\ \vdots \\ (1-\alpha^{p+1})I_m \end{bmatrix}}_{D_{y_2}} d_y(k), \quad (29)$$

where $D_{x_1} \in \mathbb{R}^{np \times n}$, $D_{x_2} \in \mathbb{R}^{np \times n}$, $D_{y_1} \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times m}$, and $D_{y_2} \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times m}$ are the auxiliary matrices with the disturbance filtering parameter, and $I_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $I_m \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are the identity matrices.

C. Target Calculation with Disturbance

The target calculation for offset-free MPC is performed by minimizing the function (12a) with respect to the following conditions:

$$x_s(k) = Ax_s(k) + Bu_s(k) + d_x^*(k), \quad (30a)$$

$$y_s(k) = Cx_s(k) + d_y^*(k). \quad (30b)$$

D. Disturbance augmented model

The second approach to designing offset-free MPC involves utilizing an augmented state-space model with a disturbance observer [12]. By incorporating disturbance into the nominal system model (8), the disturbance model can be defined as follows:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + B_d d(k), \quad (31a)$$

$$d(k+1) = d(k), \quad (31b)$$

$$y(k) = Cx(k) + C_d d(k), \quad (31c)$$

where $d(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ is the disturbance vector, $B_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_d}$ is the disturbance input matrix, $C_d \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_d}$ is the disturbance output matrix, and n_d is the number of disturbances, which must satisfy the condition $n_d \leq m$ [6].

The augmented disturbance model can be defined using an augmented state vector $z(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n+n_d}$ as:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} x(k+1) \\ d(k+1) \end{bmatrix}}_{z(k+1)} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} A & B_d \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}}_{A_a} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} x(k) \\ d(k) \end{bmatrix}}_{z(k)} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{B_a} u(k), \quad (32a)$$

$$y(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} C & C_d \end{bmatrix}}_{C_a} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} x(k) \\ d(k) \end{bmatrix}}_{z(k)}, \quad (32b)$$

where $A_a \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+n_d) \times (n+n_d)}$ is the augmented state matrix, $B_a \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+n_d) \times r}$ is the augmented input matrix, and $C_a \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n+n_d)}$ is the augmented output matrix.

The application of the Kalman filter for estimating the augmented state vector $z(k)$ yields the prediction and correction step equations (4)-(5) on the following form:

$$\hat{z}(k) = A_a \hat{z}^*(k-1) + B_a u(k-1), \quad (33)$$

$$\hat{z}^*(k) = \hat{z}(k) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} K_x \\ K_d \end{bmatrix}}_{K_a} (y(k) - C_a \hat{z}(k)), \quad (34)$$

where $K_a \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+n_d) \times m}$ is the augmented Kalman gain matrix, comprising $K_x \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ and $K_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d \times m}$.

One of the advantages of this approach lies in independent tuning of covariance matrix of the disturbance Q_d , hence the covariance matrix Q in (2) is augmented as follows:

$$\tilde{Q} = \text{cov}(w(k), w(k)) = \begin{pmatrix} Q_x & 0 \\ 0 & Q_d \end{pmatrix}, \quad (35)$$

where $\tilde{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+n_d) \times (n+n_d)}$, $Q_x \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, and $Q_d \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d \times n_d}$.

The design of offset-free MPC using the augmented disturbance model follows the standard MPC design procedure presented so far, with the state vector $x(k)$ in (9) replaced by the augmented state vector $z(k)$ in (32). Similarly, matrix A is replaced by A_a , matrix B by B_a , and matrix C by C_a .

V. VAN DE VUSSE REACTION

The Van de Vusse reaction (VVR) is a reaction scheme occurring in a Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR). The reactant cyclopentadiene (A) produces the desired product cyclopentenol (B) and undesired byproducts cyclopentanediol (C) and dicyclopentadiene (D).

The exothermic variant of the reaction is defined by the following system of nonlinear differential equations [9]:

$$\dot{c}_A = -k_1(T)c_A - k_3(T)c_A^2 + (c_{A_{in}} - c_A)u_1, \quad (36a)$$

$$\dot{c}_B = k_1(T)c_A - k_2(T)c_B - c_B u_1, \quad (36b)$$

$$\dot{T} = h_r(c_A, c_B, T) + \alpha_R(T_c - T) + (T_{in} - T)u_1, \quad (36c)$$

$$\dot{T}_c = \beta_R(T - T_c) + \gamma_R u_2. \quad (36d)$$

The mass balance equations for concentrations of the input material c_A (36a) and the desired product c_B (36b) involve the concentration of reactant in the input flow rate $c_{A_{in}}$, along with kinetic rate coefficients $k_i(T)$ that depend on the reactor temperature T according to the Arrhenius law, defined as:

$$k_i(T) = \kappa_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right) \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (37)$$

The energy balance equations of the reactor (36c) and the thermal jacket (36d) include the coolant temperature T_c , the input flow temperature T_{in} , and the reaction enthalpy $h_r(c_A, c_B, T)$, which is defined as

$$h_r(c_A, c_B, T) = -\sigma_R \Delta H_1 k_1(T) c_A - \sigma_R \Delta H_2 k_2(T) c_B - \sigma_R \Delta H_3 k_3(T) c_A^2. \quad (38)$$

Parameter values of the reaction model are detailed in [9], with the model values used in the simulation sourced from this reference.

The first input variable $u_1 = q/V_R$ is the input flow rate q normalized by the reactor volume V_R and the second input $u_2 = Q_c$ is the amount of heat removed by the coolant.

A. Linearization and Discretization

For the design of a linear MPC, it is necessary to linearize the controlled system at the chosen steady-state u_0, x_0 . The nonlinear model (36) of the chemical reactor, extended to include a process noise vector $w(t)$, can be expressed in the general form as:

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x(t), u(t)) + w(t), \quad (39)$$

where $w(t) = [w_1(t) \ w_2(t) \ w_3(t) \ w_4(t)]^T$ is the process noise, interpreted as random exogenous disturbances affecting the evolution of the four states, i.e., both concentrations and temperatures of the reaction. By linearizing (40), we obtain:

$$\Delta \dot{x}(t) = \bar{A} \underbrace{(x(t) - x_0)}_{\Delta x(t)} + \bar{B} \underbrace{(u(t) - u_0)}_{\Delta u(t)} + w(t). \quad (40)$$

The derivation of the system matrices \bar{A} and \bar{B} through linearization is detailed in [1]. The system output for the linearized stochastic model can be expressed as:

$$y(t) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_c (\Delta x(t) + x_0) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix}}_{v(t)}. \quad (41)$$

According to (41), only three states are considered controlled and measured: the concentration of the desired product c_B , the reactor temperature T , and the coolant temperature T_c .

The continuous-time linearized model (39), (41) is discretized with a sample time T_s into the form (1) such that $A = \exp(\bar{A}T_s)$ and $B = (A - I_n)\bar{A}^{-1}\bar{B}$.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

To validate the methodology, we conducted a simulation in MATLAB. We simulated a classical MPC and two variants of offset-free MPC with the nonlinear chemical reactor model as a plant, which was influenced by process noise.

The nonlinear model of the VVR reaction was simulated using the Runge-Kutta 4 method, with the numerical integration step $T_i = 0.0001$ h. The sampling time $T_s = 0.02$ h was used to discretize the linear system model and to sample the MPC and state estimator.

The discrete noise vectors $w(k)$ and $v(k)$, modeled as piecewise-constant zero-mean white noises sampled with T_s , have their covariance matrices chosen based on realistic considerations as follows:

$$Q = \text{diag}(5 \times 10^4, \ 5 \times 10^4, \ 100, \ 100), \quad (42)$$

$$R = \text{diag}(10, \ 0.1, \ 0.1). \quad (43)$$

In the second offset-free MPC approach, the covariance matrix \bar{Q} is used in the form given by (35), where we selected $Q_x = Q$ as in (42) and $Q_d = \text{diag}(500, \ 500, \ 1, \ 1)$.

For the MPC design, the prediction horizon was set to $p = 15$, and the control horizon was set to $c = 10$. The weighting matrices of the objective function were selected as follows to ensure satisfactory MPC performance, while considering the units (different orders of magnitude for concentration and temperatures) in which the individual outputs are expressed:

$$Q_y = \text{diag}(1, \ 1000, \ 1000), \quad (44)$$

$$R_d = \text{diag}(0.5, \ 0.005). \quad (45)$$

The selection of the weighting matrix for target calculation (46) depends on the choice of outputs to which priority is assigned to achieve the desired reference. In this case, the highest priority was assigned to the first two outputs, with the values for c_B and T remaining the same as in (44), while the third output T_c was given the lowest priority, and its value was reduced by two orders of magnitude compared to (44).

$$Q_s = \text{diag}(1, \ 1000, \ 10). \quad (46)$$

The disturbance filtering parameter of the offset-free MPC was appropriately chosen as $\alpha = 0.8$.

The simulation results, shown in Fig. 2-Fig. 4, compare the classical MPC (*black*) with the offset-free MPC designed using two different approaches: the state disturbance observer without disturbance filtering (*blue*), with disturbance filtering (*red*) and the augmented disturbance model (*green*). The offset-free MPC designed using the first method without

Fig. 2 Time responses of the system inputs (black – classical MPC, blue – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0$, red – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0.8$, green – offset-free MPC type 2).

Fig. 3 Time responses of the concentrations (black – classical MPC, blue – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0$, red – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0.8$, green – offset-free MPC type 2).

filtering (blue) reaches the desired steady-state value in a shorter time than the second method (green) and the first method with filtering (red), as shown in Fig. 3-Fig. 4. On the other hand, the inputs of the first method (blue) exhibit significantly higher oscillations compared to the other plots, as observed in Fig. 2. The VVR exhibits non-minimum phase behavior, evident in the concentration responses in Fig. 3, where the states counter-react to step changes in the reference signal. This property also affects the control inputs, as seen in Fig. 2, where the input signals reach their constraints during reference step changes. In Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, it can be observed that the controlled outputs with classical MPC do not always reach the target when the plant deviates from the operating point. The offset-free MPC approach reduces this permanent bias, which is caused by the mismatch between the model and the plant due to the linearization. The difference between the desired reference value and the optimized target value is visible for both MPC formulations in the coolant temperature response (Fig. 4), which is caused by the selected weighting matrix Q_s that assigns the lowest priority to the third output. Nevertheless, note that since the chemical reactor model has only two inputs, only two outputs c_B and T can be controlled to the desired reference, therefore, also the offset-free MPC exhibits a bias on the reference of T_c .

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the design of offset-free MPC using two different approaches for the nonlinear VVR. The chemical reactor model, affected by process and measurement noise, was linearized at a selected operating point and then discretized. State estimation was performed using an asymptotic Kalman filter, providing an optimal state estimate. The offset-free MPC successfully eliminated the steady-state bias between the output and the target, which arose due to the mismatch between the linearized model and the plant. Since this control using a state and output disturbance observer without filtering resulted in more oscillatory inputs compared to the control based on the augmented disturbance model, filtered disturbances were introduced into the MPC prediction. These filtered disturbances attenuated the effects of state and output noise on disturbance estimation, thereby improving overall system control performance and minimizing oscillations in the control inputs. Future work could explore the design of an offset-free nonlinear MPC with state

Fig. 4 Time responses of the temperatures (black – classical MPC, blue – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0$, red – offset-free MPC type 1 with $\alpha = 0.8$, green – offset-free MPC type 2).

estimation using an extended Kalman filter, as well as its experimental validation in laboratory conditions to assess its practical performance.

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